

Dendrochronological analysis of ship timbers from three wrecks Bi16, Bi17 & Bi18 at Bispevika, Oslo

by

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Commissioned by Sarah Fawsitt, Norsk Maritimt Museum.

Seven samples from three wrecks found during excavations at Bispevika in Oslo, named Bispevika 16, Bispevika 17, and Bispevika 18, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. The results are described in this report.

Bispevika 16, Oslo

Three samples are from the boat named Bi16 and they are all of *Quercus sp.*, oak. All samples are from planks in the boat. All three samples are dated.

Fig. 1. Three ships from Bispevika, Oslo. The chronological position of the dated samples.

All three planks are tangentially converted from the parent tree.

Plank x148 (p26 Z249002a) contains 189 tree-rings, of which 6 are sapwood rings. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that this plank was made from can be placed at c. AD 1589-1603.

Plank x321 (p28 Z249003a) contains 108 tree-rings, all heartwood. This sample is from a tree felled after AD1592.

Plank x253 (p25 Z249001a) contains 203 tree-rings, all heartwood. This sample is dated. This sample is from a tree felled after AD1585.

If the trees for the planks were all felled at the same time, then this felling took place **around AD 1592-1603** (see fig. 1).

		Z249003a	Z249001a	Z249002a	Z253001a	Z253002a	Z252002a	Z2520019
	Bi16 x321 Z249003a	*	3.17	2.15	3.08	4.06	2.58	2.76
Z249M001	Bi16 x253 Z249001a	3.17*		11.26	4.2	4.07	2.56	1.99
	Bi16 x148 Z249002a	2.15	11.26*		5.29	5.95	4.27	3.22
Z253M001	Bi18 x186 Z253001a	3.08	4.2	5.29*		14.03	3.65	3.84
	Bi18 x179 Z253002a	4.06	4.07	5.95	14.03*		5.45	2.63
	Bi17 x093 Z252002a	2.58	2.56	4.27	3.65	5.45*		1.85
	Bi17 x069 Z2520019	2.76	1.99	3.22	3.84	2.63	1.85*	

Table 1. Three ships from Bispevika, Oslo. Result of the correlation (t -value) between the tree-ring curves from each dated sample with each other.

Bispevika 17, Oslo

Two samples are from Bi17 and they are both of *Quercus sp.*, oak. Both samples are from planks in the boat. Both samples are dated.

Both planks are tangentially converted from the parent tree.

Plank x069 (p5 Z2520019) contains 90 tree-rings, all heartwood. This sample is from a tree felled after AD1567.

Plank x093 (p6 Z252002a) contains 144 tree-rings, of which 8 are sapwood rings. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that this plank was made from can be placed at c. AD 1579-1591.

If the trees for the two planks were felled at the same time, this felling took place **around AD 1579-1591**(see fig. 1).

Bispevika 18, Oslo

Two samples are from Bi18 and they are both of *Quercus sp.*, oak. Both samples are from planks in the boat. Both samples are dated.

Both planks are tangentially converted from the parent tree.

Plank x179 (p11 Z253002a) contains 194 tree-rings, of which 1 is a sapwood ring. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that this plank was made from can be placed at c. AD 1566-1580.

Plank x186 (p10 Z253001a) contains 228 tree-rings, of which 9 are sapwood rings. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that this plank was made from can be placed at c. AD 1567-1578.

If the trees for the two planks were felled at the same time, this felling took place **around AD 1567-1578** (see fig. 1).

The analysis of the three boats shows that the three are broadly contemporary, dating to the last three decades of the 16th century, each built around a decade after each other.

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Filenames	-	-	Bi16 x321 Z249003a	Bi16 x253 x148 Z249M001	Bi17 x069 Z2520019	Bi17 x093 Z252002a	Bi18 x179 x186 Z253M001	
-	start	dates	AD1477	AD1375	AD1470	AD1435	AD1339	
-	dates	end	AD1584	AD1588	AD1559	AD1578	AD1566	
Chronologies from ships								
Z157M001	AD1365	AD1565	6.17	7.15	3.09	6.39	11.08	Bispevika 12 ship Oslo 5 timbers (Daly & Daly 2016a)
Z109M001	AD1437	AD1597	4.21	5.98	-	7.19	10.57	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013c)
Z110M001	AD1342	AD1601	5.34	5.33	-	-	9.13	Barcode ship 3 BC03 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013c)
Z0302M04	AD1407	AD1591	5.40	3.24	-	4.46	8.21	Barcode ship BC02 6 timber (Daly 2014b)
Z0307M01	AD1435	AD1585	5.45	3.20	-	3.29	7.34	Barcode ship BC07 5 timber (Daly 2010b)
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	4.61	5.27	-	-	7.28	Klim Strandvraget 2 timbers (Daly 2011a)
SNorway s	AD1304	AD1895	7.29	5.18	-	5.65	7.11	South Norway ships 63 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z086M001	AD1468	AD1584	6.02	3.82	-	3.82	6.83	Havnelageret 1 Oslo boat 3 timbers (Daly 2013b)
Z0306M01	AD1418	AD1585	5.67	3.69	-	-	5.54	Barcode 6 6 timbers (Daly 2010a)
Z040M001	AD1386	AD1567	-	8.19	-	4.64	6.89	Gåsehage Randers 2 timbers (Daly 2009)
Z141M001	AD1352	AD1539	-	10.75	-	3.38	7.70	Klippan 2 shipwreck Göteborg 11 timbers (Daly 2015b)
Z0923M03	AD1328	AD1618	-	10.63	3.93	4.50	6.24	Vasa group 3 31 timbers (Daly unpubl)
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	-	10.63	-	4.41	4.05	B&W Grund Vrag 2. 2 trees (Daly 1997b, 2000b)
Z073m001	AD1385	AD1574	-	9.94	-	4.80	5.98	Barcode 14 ship Oslo 3 timbers (Daly 2011b)
Z119M001	AD1317	AD1573	3.77	8.44	4.29	5.19	3.45	Barcode Oslo ship 4 BC04 5 timbers (Daly 2015a)
Z027M002	AD1313	AD1567	-	7.48	-	3.19	5.91	Amager Strand ship 9 timbers (Daly 2008)
Z147M002	AD1363	AD1535	-	7.26	4.89	3.30	5.47	Bispevika 4 ship Oslo B3B7 5 timbers (Daly 2016d)
Z089m001	AD1399	AD1581	-	7.77	4.89	4.94	5.31	Oslo Barcode skib 5. 9 timbers (Daly 2013a)
Z0309M01	AD1395	AD1561	-	6.41	4.53	4.33	5.24	Barcode Oslo ship BC09 2 timbers (Daly 2010c)
Z177M001	AD1434	AD1518	\	5.19	\	5.25	4.79	Bispevika 14 ship Oslo 2 timbers (Daly & Daly 2016b)
Z118M002	AD1422	AD1636	4.10	4.45	-	6.78	4.70	Paléhaven I Oslo 3 timbers (Daly 2014a)
Site and master chronologies								
ZEALAND	AD452	AD1770	-	9.16	-	4.61	9.69	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	-	9.03	3.40	5.38	9.57	Ålborg østerå + boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a 2001a)
SScanM25	AD1343	AD1548	-	10.49	-	3.37	9.14	Southern Scandinavia 36 timbers (Daly unpubl)
WSwedM2	AD1344	AD1560	-	12.35	-	5.29	8.69	West Sweden 49 timbers (Daly unpubl)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	-	10.63	4.75	4.70	6.68	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
B027oak B	AD1248	AD1532	-	10.34	-	-	8.12	Gammel Strand Copenhagen B purple 21 timbers (Daly 2016e)
NB700000	AD1345	AD1538	-	10.66	-	3.37	7.61	Helsingør (Nationalmuseet)
SE08M003	AD1348	AD1634	-	9.65	4.05	4.37	7.18	Uddevallå 191 1 SU Trappan 6 timbers (Daly 2018)
B027oak E	AD1315	AD1663	-	6.68	-	4.49	8.70	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak pink 5 timbers (Daly 2016e)
8111M001	AD1350	AD1480	\	5.57	\	\	8.00	Astrup K. 13 timbers (Daly 1998b)
2M000005	AD1316	AD1514	\	7.09	\	5.20	7.58	Sjælland kirker (e.g. Daly 1998a)
H11K2M0	AD1401	AD1545	-	5.40	-	3.03	7.28	HL Koenigstr 11 4 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
SM100001	AD1310	AD1539	-	7.51	-	-	7.09	Ystad area (Lund University)
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	3.19	8.37	-	3.27	6.72	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
CD60IZ01	AD1450	AD1635	3.85	6.32	-	4.30	6.00	Ryomgård 9 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007)
LS104M01	AD1353	AD1467	\	6.60	\	\	4.25	Västra Nöbbelöv Kirke 10 timbers (Lund Uni revised Daly 2007)
N0254M01	AD1421	AD1570	-	-	-	6.02	5.23	Oslo B3B7 PINE 10 timbers (Daly 2017)
PP121M01	AD1373	AD1637	-	3.02	-	5.02	3.15	PL Oliwa Cathedral 31 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
Chronologies containing imports								
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	-	5.08	-	3.76	7.78	Fenton Tower Scotland IMPORTS 5 timbers (Crone pers comm)
81M00004	AD1350	AD1480	\	6.03	\	\	7.71	kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group 24 timber (Daly 1998c)
B028M003	AD1386	AD1576	3.37	8.79	3.01	3.97	7.42	Køge Havn 4 timbers (Daly 2013d)
2121M002	AD1052	AD1596	-	8.55	-	3.62	7.37	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001b)
21015M02	AD1305	AD1743	-	3.70	-	3.88	7.36	B&W grund 24 trees (Daly 1997a & c)
B012M001	AD1347	AD1484	\	5.16	\	-	7.29	Copenhagen Admiralgade 3 timbers (Daly 2005)
CARNCKx	AD1317	AD1588	-	4.24	-	6.46	7.68	Carnock Castle Scotland IMPORTS (Crone pers comm)
B027oak C	AD1331	AD1557	-	10.75	3.43	6.56	7.17	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 23 timbers (Daly 2016e)
q415029m	AD1356	AD1540	-	13.31	-	5.24	7.12	Evangelistas altarpiece Seville Cathedral 29 planks (Rodríguez-Trobajo & Domínguez-Delmás 2015)
4077M00Z	AD1310	AD1546	-	9.02	-	5.70	6.27	Nyborg Slot renaissance phase 38 timbers (Daly 1999, 2007)
H011M001	AD1386	AD1563	-	8.33	-	4.65	6.58	Aalborg Algade Tiendeladen hus 4 timbers (Daly 2016b)
H012M001	AD1379	AD1576	-	6.46	4.03	5.46	6.41	Sankelmarksgade Aalborg sogn 4 timbers (Daly 2016c)
B037M001	AD1337	AD1550	-	7.76	-	3.51	6.21	Favrholm Mølle 20 timbers (Daly 2016f)
H009M001	AD1410	AD1613	-	6.33	-	3.99	5.46	Strandgade Nibe bolværk A6 3 timbers (Daly 2016a)

Table 2. Three ships from Bispevika, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the tree-ring data from the ships and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Provenance

The tree-ring curves from the samples from the three boats cross-match each other as shown in table 1.

Bispevika 16

Two samples from boat Bi16 (x148 & x253) match very well together, but on visual comparison they are not similar enough to suggest that they come from the same tree. An average of these two is calculated (Z249M001) which is 214 years in length. This average is dating against a wide range of Scandinavian tree-ring datasets for oak (see table 2). The highest correlations are with chronologies from west Sweden. The third sample from Bi16 matches only weakly with the other two samples from the boat. It is dating with other tree-ring datasets from boats and ships from Oslo Harbour (see table 2).

Bispevika 17

The two tree-ring curves from Bi17 do not display significant agreement with each other (table 1). The two samples are dating with a range of tree-ring datasets for Southern Scandinavia (table 2) particularly with some of the boats from Oslo.

Bispevika 18

The tree-ring curves from the two planks from Bi18 show very high correlation (see table 1). A visual comparison of the two series does not allow the suggestion that the two are from the same tree, however. An average of the two is calculated (Z253M001) of 228 years in length. The correlation between this average and a range of tree-ring datasets is shown in table 2. The highest correlation is with two of the boats found in Oslo in recent years, particularly with Bispevika 12 and with Barcode BC01, both boats made with oaks from Southern Norway.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program 'DENDRO' (Tyers, 1997) and for the calculation of the *t*-value ('*t*-test') 'CROS' (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are used. To estimate the felling dates of the oak trees a sapwood average for Southern Norway is used (c. 15 sapwood years (-8+6)) (Christensen & Havemann 1998).

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Samples											
Z249001a	Bispevika 16 Oslo 2019151 x253 p25 hubbord QUSP	203	AD1375	AD1577	G	0	N	T	H1	1.19	after AD1585
Z249002a	Bispevika 16 Oslo 2019151 x148 p26 hubbord QUSP	189	AD1400	AD1588	G	6	N	T	S1	1.21	AD1589-1603
Z249003a	Bispevika 16 Oslo 2019151 x321 p28 hubbord QUSP	108	AD1477	AD1584	G	0	N	T	H1	1.17	after AD1592
Z2520019	Bispevika 17 Oslo 2019152 x069 p5 hubbord QUSP	90	AD1470	AD1559	F	0	N	T	H1	1.10	after AD1567
Z252002a	Bispevika 17 Oslo 2019152 x093 p6 hubbord QUSP	144	AD1435	AD1578	F	8	N	T	S1	0.97	AD1579-91
Z253001a	Bispevika 18 Oslo 2019161 x186 p10 hubbord QUSP	228	AD1339	AD1566	F	9	N	T	S1	0.70	AD1567-78
Z253002a	Bispevika 18 Oslo 2019161 x179 p11 hubbord QUSP	194	AD1367	AD1560	F	1	N	T	S1	0.80	AD1566-80
Averages											
Z249M001	Bispevika 16 Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2019)	214	AD1375	AD1588						1.23	
Z253M001	Bispevika 18 Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2019)	228	AD1339	AD1566						0.76	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies sp.</i> , fir.											
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